

Analytical Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form By RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

A reliable and efficient Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method has been developed for the simultaneous estimation of Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide in bulk and tablet dosage forms. The chromatographic separation was performed using an Altima C18 column (4.6 × 150 mm, 5 μm) with a mobile phase consisting of methanol and acetonitrile (50:50 v/v). The flow rate was optimized to 1 ml/min, and the detection was carried out at 230 nm. The injection volume was 10 μL, with a run time of 14 minutes. The method was validated for various parameters, including linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, and robustness. The results demonstrated that the method is precise, accurate, and capable of providing good resolution for both drugs in their bulk and tablet forms. The method offers a simple, rapid, and reproducible solution for routine analysis and quality control of Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide in pharmaceutical formulations.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, nadolol, Bendroflumethiazide, analytical method development, validation, pharmaceutical formulations, quality control, chromatographic separation, tablet dosage form.

INTRODUCTION

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) was derived from the classical column chromatography and is one of the most important tools of analytical chemistry today^[1]. In the modern pharmaceutical industry, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is the major and integral analytical tool applied in all stages of drug discovery, development, and production^[2]. The analytical method for drug analysis that is growing the fastest is HPLC. ^[3] HPLC is the preferred technique for determining the peak purity of new chemical entities, detecting changes in reactions during scale-up or synthesis processes, evaluating novel formulations, and carrying out quality assurance and control on the finished pharmaceutical product. ^[4] The principle behind HPLC is that when a mixture of various compounds is added to the mobile phase and allowed to pass over a stationary phase, the compounds move at varying rates and separate according to the relative affinities for both the mobile and stationary phases ^[5]

The Goal of HPLC method is to try & separate, quantify the main drug, any reaction impurities, all available synthetic intermediates and any degradants. Nadolol is a white crystalline powder. Chemically it is known (2R,3S)-5-[3-(tert-butylamino)-2-hydroxypropoxy]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro naphthalene-2,3-diol. It is freely soluble in ethanol, soluble in hydrochloric acid, slightly soluble in water and in chloroform, and very slightly soluble in sodium hydroxide.^[6] Nadolol is a non-selective beta-adrenergic antagonist and has antihypertensive and antiarrhythmic properties.^[7] The catecholamines norepinephrine and adrenaline are inhibited by nadolol's competitive blocking of beta-1 adrenergic receptors in the heart and vascular smooth muscle, which has detrimental inotropic and chronotropic effects. Unlike many other beta-adrenergic blocking agents, nadolol is not metabolized by the liver and is excreted unchanged, principally by the kidneys. The half-life of therapeutic doses of nadolol is about 20 to 24 hours, permitting once-daily dosage.^[8]

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Figure 1: Chemical Structure of Nadolol

Bendroflumethiazide is a long-acting agent, also known as Bendroflumethiazide, belonging to the class of thiazide diuretics with antihypertensive activity. It is soluble in alcohol and sodium hydroxide, and insoluble in hydrochloric acid, water, and chloroform. Chemically, it is 3-benzyl-1,1-dioxo-6-(trifluoromethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-1λ6,2,4-benzothiadiazine-7-sulfonamide.^[9]

Bendroflumethiazide, a thiazide diuretic, removes excess water from the body by increasing how often you urinate (pass water) and also widens the blood vessels, which helps to reduce blood pressure. It inhibits Na⁺/Cl⁻ reabsorption from the distal convoluted tubules in the kidneys.^[10]

Figure 2: Chemical Structure of Bendroflumethiazide

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Nadolol pure drug [API], Bendroflumethiazide pure drug [API] were procured from Sun Pharma, provided by Sura Pharma labs. The chemicals utilized in this estimation were obtained from Merck.

INSTRUMENTATION:

The development and method validation were conducted using a WATERS HPLC, specifically the model 2695 system equipped with a 996 TDA detector. The system includes Empower 2 software.

OBJECTIVE:

- To develop a new, simple, sensitive, accurate, and economical analytical method for the simultaneous estimation of Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide in pure and pharmaceutical dosage forms.
- To validate the proposed method in accordance with USP and ICH guidelines for the intended analytical application, i.e., to apply the proposed method for analysis of the Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide in pure and pharmaceutical dosage form Table 1: Chromatographic Conditions.

Mobile phase	Methanol: ACN (50:50V/V/V)
Flow rate	1 ml/min
Column	Altima C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5μm)
Wave length	230 nm
Column temperature	30°C
Injection volume	10μL
Run time	10 mins

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide working standard into a 10 ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7 ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 0.1 ml of the above Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 500 ml (50%) of Methanol and 500 ml (50%) of Acetonitrile were mixed and degassed in a digital ultrasonicator for 10 minutes, and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Preparation of Standard Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nadolol and 10 mg of Bendroflumethiazide working standard into

a 10 ml of clean dry volumetric flasks, add about 7 ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.15 ml of Nadolol and 0.3 ml of Bendroflumethiazide from the above stock solutions into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Take the average weight of one Tablet and crush it in a mortar using a pestle and weight 10 mg equivalent weight of Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide sample into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, and add about 7 ml of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely, and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. Further pipette 0.3 ml of Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide above stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS:

1. Linearity

Figure 3: Calibration Graph for Nadolol

2. ACCURACY:

Table-4: The accuracy results for Nadolol

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	1543793	15	15.2	101.9	100.9%
100%	3035883	30	30.4	101.4	
150%	4451005	45	44.7	99.4	

Table 2: Linearity Result for Nadolol

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
0	0
5	1010252
10	2049374
15	3072706
20	3921068
25	4952813

Figure 4: Calibration Graph for Bendroflumethiazide

Table 3: Linearity result for Bendroflumethiazide

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
0	0
10	8040807
20	14318417
30	21087985
40	27913928
50	34584741

Table-5: The accuracy results for Bendroflumethiazide

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	1084420	30	30.07	100.2	99.6%
100%	2096069	60	59.6	99.4	
150%	3112684	90	89.3	99.3	

3. PRECISION:**1. Repeatability****Table 6: Repeatability result**

HPLC Injection Replicates	AUC for Nadolol	AUC for Bendroflumethiazide
1	3569412	3582264
2	3465125	3586491
3	3598154	3598154
4	3586491	3564125
5	3582694	3569412
6	3586491	3564125
Mean	3564727	3577428
Std.Dev	49658.89	13807.88
%RSD	1.39	0.386

2. INTERMEDIATE PRECISION:**Table 7: Result for Nadolol**

No. of Replicates	Intra-Day		Inter-Day	
	Mean	%RSD	Mean	%RSD
06	3455929	0.5	3455929	0.5

Table 8: Result for Bendroflumethiazide

No. of Replicates	Intra-Day		Inter-Day	
	Mean	%RSD	Mean	%RSD
06	15404779	1.6	15404814	1.4

4. LIMIT OF DETECTION [LOD] & LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION [LOQ]:

The detection limit [LOD] & quantification [LOQ] may be expressed as:

$$LOD = 3.3 \times \sigma / s L$$

$$LOQ = 10 \times \sigma / S$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

The Minimum concentration at which the analyte can be detected [LOD] & Quantified [LOQ] were found to be 1.9 μ g/ml & 3.9 μ g/ml respectively for nadolol.

The LOD were found to be 2.60 μ g/ml & LOQ were found to be 6.5 μ g/ml for bendroflumethiazide

5. ROBUSTNESS:

A small change in chromatographic condition such as change in flow rate, temperature, wave-length are studied to determine the robustness of the method.

Table-9: Results for Robustness for Nadolol

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	3425413	2.088	5568.2	1.0
Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	3425282	3.111	5922.2	1.2
Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	3517879	1.880	5868.8	1.2
Less aqueous phase	3175485	3.101	5836.2	1.2
More aqueous phase	3365431	1.881	5282.6	1.1

Table-10 : Results for Robustness for Bendroflumethiazide

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	2029854	6.068	5359.2	1.1
Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	1738319	7.101	5999.1	1.2
Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	1638304	5.007	5989.2	1.1
Less aqueous phase	1973724	7.108	5387.2	1.1
More aqueous phase	2102838	5.008	5938.1	1.1

6. SYSTEM SUITABILITY

Table-11: Results of system suitability for Nadolol

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Nadolol	2.191	3569412	567917	5568.0	1.0
2	Nadolol	2.186	3465125	517719	6359.2	1.1
3	Nadolol	2.189	3598154	567933	5565.5	1.0
4	Nadolol	2.190	3586491	517733	5355.2	1.1
5	Nadolol	2.184	3582694	567917	6348.0	1.0
Mean			3560375			
Std. Dev			54225.61			
% RSD			1.523031			

Table-11: Results of system suitability for Bendroflumethiazide

S. No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Bendroflumethiazide	6.090	3582264	567917	5568.0	1.0
2	Bendroflumethiazide	6.095	3586491	517719	5359.2	1.1
3	Bendroflumethiazide	6.091	3598154	567933	5565.5	1.0
4	Bendroflumethiazide	6.092	3564125	517733	5355.2	1.1
5	Bendroflumethiazide	6.089	3569412	562173	5568.0	1.0
Mean			3580089			
Std. Dev			13609.81			
% RSD			0.380153			

7. ASSAY:

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

Table 13: Showing Assay Results

S. No	Name of Compound	Label Claim	Amount Taken	% Purity
1	Nadolol	15 mg	12.89	100.1%
2	Bendroflumethiazide	20 mg	18.9	99.95%

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

The developed RP-HPLC method provides a simple, accurate, precise, and reproducible approach for the estimation of Nadolol and Bendroflumethiazide in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. The method's validation outcomes confirmed its reliability and robustness, making it suitable for routine quality control, stability testing, and analytical studies of the drugs. Its efficiency, minimal run time, and reproducibility establish it as an effective analytical tool for pharmaceutical industries and research laboratories. Chromatographic separation was achieved using an Altima C18 column (4.6 × 150 mm, 5 μm) with a mobile phase of methanol and acetonitrile (50:50 v/v). The optimized conditions included a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min, detection wavelength of 230 nm, injection volume of 10 μl, and a run time of 14 minutes. The method was validated as per ICH guidelines for parameters such as linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, and robustness. The results confirmed that the method produced sharp and well-resolved peaks for both drugs, demonstrating suitability for simultaneous analysis.

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